

***Juglares* — The Role of Geographic Mobility, Gender, Age, Institutional Research Profiles, and Local Labor Market on the Career Performance of the Scientific Workforce in Colombia**

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Abstract

This study examines whether geographic mobility within Colombia functions as a mechanism for improving career performance. Using open administrative data from the Colombian Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MinCiencias), the analysis tracks 40,485 researcher–assessment observations across six national evaluation calls between 2013 and 2021. Researchers are classified into ordered ranks: Junior, Associate, and Senior, allowing career performance to be analyzed in relation to inter-city mobility and a set of lagged individual, institutional, and local labor market characteristics. Within-country mobility in Colombia is rare and not associated with accelerated promotion. Ordinal regression models reveal that the effects of mobility differ across career stages. Junior researchers who move are more likely to remain Junior, while Associate researchers who relocate face an increased risk of being reclassified downward rather than progressing to Senior rank. Institutional context emerges as a stronger correlation of career outcomes than mobility itself. Local labor market conditions also matter, but primarily for early-career researchers. Mobility appears more disruptive than rewarding in the short to medium term, particularly for researchers in early career phases. These results imply that policies promoting mobility without accompanying institutional support risk exacerbating instability and regional concentration, rather than fostering equitable development of scientific capacity.

Keywords: Academic Mobility; Geographic Mobility; Research Performance; Science Policy; Colombia.

1. Introduction

The *juglar* vallenato was historically an itinerant wanderer, traveling by mule from town to town across the Caribbean coastal region of Colombia to sing about love, local chronicles, and nature. This cultural archetype raises a compelling question: are modern Colombian researchers functioning as *juglares* of science within their national territory?

Academic mobility is a key factor in science policy, promoting intellectual collaboration, innovative knowledge production and transfer, and the internationalization of national science systems (Cavalli & Teichler, 2015; Gureyev et al., 2020; Ito et al., 2025; Momeni et al., 2022; Morano-Foadi, 2005; Soete et al., 2021; Sugimoto et al., 2017). It has also become a prominent subject in quantitative science studies, where the most relevant topics include the development of methodological approaches, the flows of academic migration, the impact of academic mobility,

factors driving academic mobility, and historical perspectives (Gureyev et al., 2020). Despite this, most research has been directed toward international mobility, highlighting a limited understanding of the dynamics of national scientific workforce mobility in middle- and low-income countries (Liu et al., 2024).

To clarify, migration and mobility, though related, differ primarily in their permanence. According to Teichler (2015), migration implies a permanent relocation, domestic or abroad, such as a scientist moving from one country of citizenship to another to take up a permanent research position. In contrast, mobility refers to non-permanent or repeated movements without a permanent change in residence, such as a scientist participating in an international research exchange for a few months (Teichler, 2015).

Regarding exceptional studies on national mobility, evidence from the United States indicates that professors are more likely to move to institutions with higher research intensity and from rural to urban areas. Notably, female professors are more frequently relocating within the same geographic region than their male counterparts (Yan et al., 2020). At Washington State University, researchers showed high mobility rates, with domestic movers demonstrating greater citation impacts than international movers (Payumo et al., 2018). In Italy, the centralized and non-competitive university system results in lower post-mobility performance, particularly for less productive researchers (Abramo et al., 2022). Faculty members at Turkish public universities, particularly women, older individuals, and those in major cities or well-established institutions, are less likely to relocate nationally (Yuret, 2023).

Tuning the attention to Latin America, the signing of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) increased the flow of Mexican inventors to multinational companies, exacerbating the brain drain, while regional disparities in mobility persist, with Mexico City as a key destination (Aboites & Díaz, 2018). Over time, migration intensity has decreased, but the diversity and density of migration networks across Mexican states have increased (Miranda-González et al., 2020).

This study focuses on the scientific workforce mobility in Colombia, a sizable country with an area of 1.1 million square kilometers, a territory sufficient to encompass the combined areas of Germany, Italy, the United Kingdom, and Romania. Beyond its significant territorial size, Colombia presents several characteristics relevant to this analysis: a scientific system that shows measurable efficiency in research output despite scarce financial resources, and a protracted history of intense forced internal displacement stemming from an armed conflict started in the 1960s (Cortés & Ramírez Cajiao, 2024; SCImago, 2020; UNHCR, 2023).

This national context is reflected in the concentration of human capital, as researchers in Colombia originate from over 866 distinct municipalities; however, the majority are ultimately employed in the three largest cities: Bogotá, Medellín, and Cali (MinCiencias, 2022). This scenario provides a pertinent case study for advancing the research agenda on the internal mobility of researchers and the structural factors that influence their career progression.

This study aims to contribute to the understanding of national academic mobility factors by analyzing the association between researchers' mobility patterns and subsequent changes in their research career performance. We access open governmental data maintained by the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MinCiencias) rather than relying solely on canonical bibliographic sources like WoS or Scopus. In particular, we try to answer the following research question:

RQ: How is geographic mobility between cities and covariates, such as individual characteristics, institutional research profiles, and local labor market conditions associated with Colombian researchers' performance within the MinCiencias ranking system?

Following this introduction, the study's structure transitions into the methodology section. This section will include a detailed description of the open-access data repository from MinCiencias, derived from the national research groups assessment, and an explanation of the analytical methods to be applied. Subsequently, we present the results and then discuss them in relation to the existing literature. The final section, the conclusions, will address the study's limitations and outline the agenda for future research.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data

We used open-access datasets curated and issued by MinCiencias. These datasets provide information from national assessments conducted in 2013, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2021. There were no national assessments conducted by MinCiencias in 2016, 2018, and 2020. Our analysis draws on socioeconomic data and academic career data for Colombian researchers. This analysis incorporates two specific datasets: one detailing research groups and another detailing researchers. The links to both datasets are shared below:

- National Groups Assessments, 21 columns, ~30,000 rows¹
- National Researchers Assessment, 30 columns, ~77,000 rows²

MinCiencias (2023) launched a dashboard titled '*La Ciencia en Cifras*' (Science in Numbers)³ to explore the raw data contained in the dataset displayed above, among other subjects. Colombian researchers are evaluated as units within the national evaluation system, categorized into Junior, Associate, Senior, or Emeritus ranks based on criteria such as academic output, leadership, and mentoring. Researchers update their portfolios on the national platform (CvLAC), detailing their disciplinary expertise and research outputs, with oversight from institutional and research group leadership. It must be noted that academic rank progression does not influence salary or career advancement within their employing institutions (Vasen et al., 2023).

We also used the national statistics of the labor market issued by the Colombian National Statistical Office (DANE) (DANE, 2025). The national household survey (*GEIH*) is a continuous, national, probabilistic, multi-stage, and stratified household survey designed to generate official statistics on the labor market, household income, monetary poverty, and the socio-demographic characteristics of the resident population. The methodology utilizes concepts adapted from the International Labour Organization (ILO) standards, particularly the resolutions of the International Conference of Labour Statisticians (CIET), providing key indicators such as the Global Participation Rate, the Unemployment Rate, and measures of sub-utilization of the labor force. Operating with an annual sample of approximately 315,000 households, the most recent iteration is the GEIH Framework 2018, which incorporated a revised sampling design based on the 2018 National Population and Housing Census (CNPV) and introduced enhancements for the identification and measurement of population groups such as the campesino, LGBTI, and disabled populations. The justification for the inclusion of this data set will be detailed in the following

¹ <https://www.datos.gov.co/d/hrhc-c4wu>, last accessed on December 24, 2025.

² <https://www.datos.gov.co/d/bqtm-4y2h>, last accessed on December 24, 2025.

³ <https://minciencias.gov.co/la-ciencia-en-cifras>, last accessed on December 24, 2025.

subsection.

2.2 Method and variables

Because of the ordered nature of the dependent variable (researcher rank: *Junior*, *Associate*, *Senior*), we implemented an ordinal logistic regression model. The underlying assumption is the existence of a latent continuous variable that represents the unobserved “research recognition” or status of each researcher. This latent variable is modeled as a linear function of three sets of covariates: *individual*, *institutional*, and *contextual* factors, plus a random error term with zero mean and unit variance. Observed performance ranks (*Junior*, *Associate*, *Senior*) arise from this latent variable crossing estimated cutpoints that partition the continuous scale into discrete ordered categories.

Under the proportional odds specification, the cumulative probabilities of being at or below a given rank are linked to the covariates through the standard logistic function. In this framework, the odds ratios associated with each predictor are assumed to be constant across the cumulative splits of the ranking (*Junior versus Associate or Senior*, and *Junior or Associate versus Senior*). The initial model is estimated under the assumption of proportional odds.

The explanatory variables are systematically organized into three analytical domains, i.e., individual, institutional, and contextual, to capture the multifaceted factors influencing academic mobility.

Individual-level variables: standard controls for human capital and professional standing immediately preceding the observed mobility event. These include:

- Gender, introduced to test for systematic differences in mobility patterns and their outcomes across genders, is a critical consideration in national academic labor markets and career advancements (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023). The gender is auto-reported by each researcher in their individual profile; there is no algorithm implementation to infer this individual characteristic.
- Age is operationalized as years past the age of majority in Colombia (age18), providing a centered metric for accumulated experience and career stage relevant to the local context (Cortés et al., 2024a, 2024b).
- The number of institutional affiliations functions as a proxy for the size and density of the researcher’s collaboration and institutional network, where a broader network is hypothesized to increase the potential for external job opportunities and subsequent mobility (Azoulay et al., 2017; Newman, 2001, 2004).
- The previous researcher rank is included with both linear and quadratic components (.L and .Q) to rigorously test for potential non-linear effects of initial academic standing on mobility propensity (*accumulated advantages*), acknowledging that both very junior and highly established researchers may exhibit distinct mobility behaviors compared to intermediate ranks (Merton, 1988; Merton, 1968). And finally,
- Research area, categorized into six distinct disciplinary fields, controls for heterogeneity in field-specific labor market dynamics and mobility norms. The classification of research groups and their affiliated researcher into grand disciplinary areas and disciplines is based on the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Fields of Science (FOS) framework (OECD, 2015). This framework collectively comprises 219 disciplines. The distribution of disciplines across these areas is as follows: Medical and Health Sciences (60), Natural Sciences (48), Engineering and Technology (46), Social

Sciences (29), Humanities (22), and Agricultural Sciences (14). This assignment addresses, for example, the difficulties in associating authors with a specific discipline that are observed in other co-authorship approaches, as authors do not typically declare their discipline in publications (Wagner et al., 2011).

All individual variables, except for gender and research area, are measured from the ranking call immediately before any observed city move, a lagging strategy employed to mitigate endogeneity and establish the temporal sequence of conditions preceding the mobility decision.

The Institutional variables capture the organizational context and academic capital of the researcher's previous affiliated institution. These include:

- The concentration of research activity by field is measured by an index of specialization (*researcher_area_hhi_mean_11*), calculated as the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) (Herfindahl, 1950) of research areas within the institution. This variable assesses the extent to which institutional focus influences a researcher's decision to relocate for disciplinary alignment or diversification.
- The concentration of academic capital is proxied by the distribution of researcher ranks within the institution (*researcher_rank_hhi_mean_11*), where higher values signify a greater share of high-ranking researchers. This index tests for the presence of institutional "bottleneck" effects or prestige effects, which may respectively act as a push or a pull factor for geographic movement. These institutional metrics are lagged to reflect the organizational environment before the mobility observation (Cortés & Andrade, 2022; Larivière et al., 2010).

Contextual variables integrate external labor market pressure into the model. The local unemployment rate (*unemployment_rate_11*) at the city level is included as a measure of local job market pressure and economic constraints. This variable captures regional economic conditions that may influence the decision to pursue mobility, such as limited local career opportunities or the comparative attractiveness of potential destination cities (Bettencourt et al., 2007, 2010; Verginer & Riccaboni, 2021). By lagging this variable, the model ensures that the observed economic environment reflects conditions in effect at the time the researcher considered the mobility transition, thereby maintaining the established temporal precedence required for robust causal inference in this econometric specification.

The central variable of interest is a binary indicator for scientific mobility, defined as a change of city between two consecutive assessment calls (i.e., moved). We explicitly frame this variable as a measure of conditional association rather than a causal driver of performance. We acknowledge that mobility decisions are likely endogenous, potentially shaped by unobserved factors that simultaneously influence career outcomes; however, the limitations of the available administrative data—specifically the lack of valid instrumental variables or exogenous shocks—preclude the feasible application of structural approaches to correct for selection bias. Consequently, our model estimates performance differences conditional on pre-move individual and institutional characteristics. The resulting coefficient for mobility should be interpreted as the adjusted probability of rank progression associated with the event of moving, rather than a direct treatment effect isolated from selection processes.

The final dataset contains 40,485 observations corresponding to researcher–call instances. Descriptive statistics for all variables included in the model are summarized in Table 1. In sum, mobile researchers are a minority of the sample, accounting for 2.7% (n=1,081) of the total sample. The distribution of researcher rank is significantly associated with the movement event. Junior researchers, who constitute 48.6% of the overall sample, represent a high 67.3% of the individuals

in the moving cohort, indicating a substantial tendency toward mobility among early-career researchers.

Senior researchers exhibit lower geographic mobility compared to their early-career counterparts. Although this group constitutes 19.8% of the total population, they represent only 10.5% of the mobile cohort. Statistical analysis confirms that age is a decisive factor in these migration patterns (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$). The mean age of the moving group is 20.7 years (standard deviation = 7.8), significantly lower than the mean age of 26.8 years (standard deviation = 9.5) observed in the non-moving group.

Furthermore, a significant association exists between the primary research area and researcher movement. Research fields such as Natural Sciences (27.5%) and Engineering and Technology (22.1%) contribute the largest percentages to the mobile cohort. In contrast, the Medical and Health Sciences area exhibits lower comparative mobility, accounting for 10.4% of the moved group despite comprising 16.6% of the overall sample. Both the research area concentration index and the researcher rank concentration index also show significant differences between the two groups (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$). The variables of gender and the unemployment rate, however, do not exhibit a statistically significant difference between the researchers who moved and those who did not.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the ordinal logistic regression variables

Variable	Total	Moved = 0	Moved = 1	Sig. Test
No. of observations	40,723	39,642 (97.3%)	1,081 (2.7%)	
researcher_rank				*** C
Junior	19,780 (48.6%)	19,052 (48.1%)	728 (67.3%)	
Associate	12,874 (31.6%)	12,635 (31.9%)	239 (22.1%)	
Senior	8,069 (19.8%)	7,955 (20.1%)	114 (10.5%)	
gender (= male)	25,891 (63.6%)	25,192 (63.5%)	699 (64.7%)	F
age18_l1	26.626 (9.546)	26.788 (9.535)	20.689 (7.898)	*** K
research_area				*** C
agricultural sciences	1,970 (4.8%)	1,888 (4.8%)	82 (7.6%)	
engineering and technology	8,242 (20.2%)	8,003 (20.2%)	239 (22.1%)	
humanities	2,607 (6.4%)	2,531 (6.4%)	76 (7.0%)	
medical and health sciences	6,756 (16.6%)	6,644 (16.8%)	112 (10.4%)	
natural sciences	9,997 (24.5%)	9,700 (24.5%)	297 (27.5%)	
social sciences	11,151 (27.4%)	10,876 (27.4%)	275 (25.4%)	
moved (= 1)	1,081 (2.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1,081 (100.0%)	*** F
research_area_hhi_mean_l1	0.295 (0.115)	0.295 (0.115)	0.296 (0.092)	*** K
researcher_rank_hhi_mean_l1	0.461 (0.088)	0.461 (0.088)	0.469 (0.088)	*** K
unemployment_rate_l1	9.628 (1.776)	9.630 (1.770)	9.561 (1.984)	K

Note: K) Kruskal-Wallis test, F) Fisher's exact test, C) Chi-Square test.

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Figure 1 shows the correspondence between the birth department (jurisdictional equivalent of an estate in the USA) of researchers and residence at the first national call record, 2013, via alluvial visualization (Mauri et al., 2017). As previously mentioned in the 1. Introduction, Bogotá, D.C. exhibits the highest magnitude of both retention and attraction; while it retains a substantial component of its native population, it experiences a net expansion to 7,962 individuals, fueled by substantial inflows from nearly every peripheral department. Antioquia follows a similar trajectory of high internal consistency and positive net growth. In contrast, departments like Boyacá and Caldas show notable emigration patterns, where the narrowing of their destination nodes relative to their origin nodes indicates a scientific workforce labor migration toward the capital and the

Valle del Cauca. The intricate “mesh” in the center of the diagram highlights that while large hubs maintain high spatial inertia, smaller departments such as Chocó and Putumayo are characterized by highly dispersed, low-magnitude flows, reflecting a fragmented migratory pattern where residents are pulled toward multiple competing urban centers rather than a single destination.

This visualization has limitations. Given that the median year of birth for the sample is 1975, the researchers reached a median age of 38 years by 2013, suggesting that their department of residence in that year is likely to represent an intermediate stage rather than a primary or final professional location. Despite this temporal constraint, the data shows a clear pattern in the distribution of human capital. While researchers in Colombia originate from more than 866 distinct municipalities, a substantial majority of this population eventually moves or stays within the three largest urban centers: Bogotá, Medellín (the capital of Antioquia), and Cali (the capital of Valle del Cauca).

Figure 1: Correspondence between birth department and residence at the first national call record, 2013

3. Results

3.1 Model diagnostics and proportional odds assumption

After estimating the initial proportional odds model, the study assesses the validity of the parallel lines assumption using the Brant test (Brant, 1990). The test statistic (Chi-square = 1,105.69 with 15 degrees of freedom, $p < 0.001$) provides clear evidence that the proportional odds assumption does not hold. This indicates that the effect of certain predictors, including *moved*, is not constant across the different cumulative splits of the ranking. Substantively, the impact of moving to another city on the probability of transitioning from Junior to Associate is not the same as its impact on the transition from Associate to Senior.

In response to this diagnostic result, the analysis employs an “unrestricted” ordinal logistic model, in which selected coefficients are allowed to vary across the two thresholds (*Junior|Associate* and *Associate|Senior*). This model relaxes the proportional odds constraint while preserving the ordered structure of the outcome. A likelihood-ratio comparison between the restricted (proportional odds) and unrestricted specifications yields a highly significant result (LR statistic = 911, $df = 13$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that allowing heterogeneous effects across thresholds substantially improves model fit. Information criteria (AIC and BIC) and log-likelihood values also favor the unrestricted model. The main substantive conclusions are therefore drawn from this more flexible specification, summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Restricted and unrestricted ordinal logistic model results

	Restricted model	Unrestricted model	
		Junior Associate	Associate Senior
gender: male	0.17 (0.02)***	-0.14 (0.03)***	-0.30 (0.04)***
age18_l1	0.01 (0.00)***	0.01 (0.00)***	
n_affiliations_l1	0.16 (0.02)***	-0.18 (0.02)***	-0.18 (0.03)***
researcher_rank_l1.L	3.97 (0.04)***	-3.12 (0.06)***	-3.59 (0.04)***
researcher_rank_l1.Q	0.41 (0.02)***	0.22 (0.04)***	-0.73 (0.03)***
research_area: engineering and technology	0.38 (0.06)***	-0.43 (0.06)***	-0.25 (0.09)**
research_area: humanities	-0.26 (0.07)***	0.14 (0.08)	0.91 (0.13)***
research_area: medical and health sciences	0.21 (0.06)***	-0.15 (0.07)*	-0.35 (0.09)***
research_area: natural sciences	0.11 (0.06)	-0.05 (0.06)	-.22 (0.09)*
research_area: social sciences	0.03 (0.06)***	-0.14 (0.06)*	0.39 (0.09)***
moved	-0.38 (0.08)***	0.43 (0.08)***	0.19 (0.14)
research_area_hhi_mean_l1	-0.23 (0.10)*	0.04 (0.12)	(0.88 (0.18)***
researcher_rank_hhi_mean_l1	-1.09 (0.14)***	0.87 (0.15)***	2.79 (0.27)***
unemployment_rate_l1	-0.02 (0.01)**	0.03 (0.01)***	-0.01 (0.01)
Junior Associate	-1.62 (0.11)***		
Associate Senior	1.05 (0.11)***		
Intercept		-1.22 (0.12)***	0.31 (0.18)
AIC	56,744.95	55,849.47	
BIC	56,882.68	56,109.12	
Log Likelihood	-28,356.47	-27,900.74	
Num. Obs.	40,485	40,485	

*The suffixes _l1 in each variable refer to the observed values of the variable in the call immediately preceding the one in which the researcher’s city transfer was identified. The dependent variable is the researcher’s ranking on a given date. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.*

3.2 Individual factors

At the individual level, age (*age18_11*) is positively but weakly associated with upward movement in the ranking. The estimated coefficient for age in the unrestricted model is small but statistically significant, indicating that professional longevity contributes marginally to career progression. In contrast, the number of affiliations (*n_affiliations_11*) has a negative association with advancement. Although more affiliations could be interpreted as a larger personal network, the results indicate that, in the Colombian evaluation system, having multiple affiliations tends to reduce the likelihood of moving to a higher rank.

The introduction of linear (.L) and quadratic (.Q) terms for previous rank reveals nonlinear effects of initial conditions. For the *Junior|Associate* threshold, the negative coefficient on the linear term and the positive coefficient on the quadratic term suggest that modest improvements in previous rank do not translate straightforwardly into higher probabilities of reaching the Senior category. The system appears to penalize researchers who demonstrate incremental gains but fail to surpass critical thresholds of productivity or quality. As the previous rank increases, the positive quadratic component gradually offsets the negative linear effect, creating a pattern of inertia toward the extremes: researchers tend to remain either in the lower or upper ranks rather than stabilizing in intermediate positions.

For the *Associate|Senior* threshold, both the linear and quadratic components of the previous rank are negative. This pattern is consistent with a reduced probability of remaining in the Associate category over time. Instead, the evaluation system appears to discourage researchers from achieving the intermediate rank, in a context where outcomes depend not only on absolute production but also on relative positioning within a competitive field.

Differences are also observed across research areas. Compared with the reference category, some fields, such as engineering and technology or medical and health sciences, exhibit positive associations with higher ranks at certain thresholds, whereas humanities and social sciences display patterns that sometimes favor and sometimes hinder advancement, depending on the specific transition considered. These heterogeneous effects suggest that the evaluation criteria interact with field-specific publication practices, collaboration patterns, and recognition mechanisms.

3.3 Institutional factors

Institutional characteristics play a central role in shaping researchers' performance trajectories. The concentration of research activity in specific areas, as measured by the specialization index (*research_area_hhi_mean_11*), tends to be positively associated with higher ranks, although the strength of this association varies by threshold and is not always statistically robust. More consistent patterns emerge for the concentration of academic capital (*researcher_rank_hhi_mean_11*). The index capturing the internal distribution of ranks within institutions shows large and statistically significant coefficients, especially for the Associate threshold. A higher concentration of senior researchers within an institution increases the chances that an individual researcher will occupy a higher rank.

This result can be interpreted as evidence of cumulative advantage within institutional contexts. Being embedded in institutions with a high density of recognized researchers may facilitate access to resources, collaboration networks, and mentoring that enhance individual performance and visibility in the evaluation system. At the same time, it may indicate that MinCiencias' classification process itself reinforces existing institutional hierarchies, granting more recognition to researchers affiliated with already prestigious institutions.

3.4 Contextual labor market conditions

The city-level unemployment rate (*unemployment_rate_11*) is used to approximate the pressure exerted by the broader labor market on academic careers. The results indicate that higher unemployment rates are associated with changes in the probabilities of moving across ranks, which differ by career stage. For Junior researchers, higher unemployment appears to favor upward mobility, which may reflect a stronger effort to consolidate an academic position when alternative employment opportunities are scarce. Junior researchers in more adverse labor markets may increase their productivity or prioritize activities that more directly align with evaluation criteria to secure or stabilize their positions within universities.

For researchers in higher ranks, the relationship between unemployment and mobility is weaker and less systematic. In some specifications, unemployment has a positive association with transitions that destabilize intermediate positions, such as moving backward from Associate to Junior or failing to reach Senior, although these effects are not consistently significant. Overall, unemployment acts as a contextual pressure that is more consequential for early-career researchers than for those who have already established themselves in the upper tiers of the ranking system.

3.5 Scientific mobility and researcher ranking

The primary focus of the study is the relationship between geographic mobility and researchers' rankings. The unrestricted model introduces a mobility indicator that distinguishes researchers who changed cities between two assessment calls from those who remained in the same location. The estimated coefficients for the mobility variable are positive at both thresholds, but only statistically significant for the transition from Junior to Associate. This suggests that, on average, relocating to another city is associated with differences in the likelihood of occupying specific ranks; however, these differences do not uniformly correspond to promotions.

To clarify these patterns, the study computes and plots the marginal probabilities of being classified as Junior, Associate, or Senior, conditional on the researcher's previous rank and mobility status (Figure 2.). The first panel (left) examines researchers previously classified as Junior. The probability of remaining in the Junior category is generally high, and this likelihood is observed to be even higher when a Junior researcher relocates to another city. Thus, geographic mobility appears linked to a consolidation of the initial position rather than characterizing a rapid pathway to Associate or Senior ranks. For researchers who were already Associates, the baseline probability of being reclassified as Junior is relatively low (around one-fifth), but this probability corresponds to a higher value following a city move. For Senior researchers, the probability of falling into the Junior category is minimal and varies little with mobility status. Taken together, the evidence suggests that mobility is not associated with early promotion; instead, it correlates with retention in entry-level ranks and a higher likelihood of downgrading for those in intermediate positions.

The second panel (center) focuses on the probability of being categorized as an Associate. For Junior researchers, moving to another city coincides with a significantly lower probability of being classified as Associate or Senior in the subsequent call. For Associate researchers, mobility is also linked to a lower probability of maintaining the Associate category. When considered alongside the results from the first panel, it becomes clear that moving to a different city is associated with a higher likelihood that Associate researchers will be reclassified as Junior rather than promoted to Senior. For Senior researchers, the association between mobility and the probability of becoming an Associate is small but positive, indicating a slight difference in the likelihood of a downgrade

to the intermediate rank. Overall, mobility in the middle stage of the career appears to coincide with instability: researchers who move exhibit a greater likelihood of downward movement in the ranking, accompanied by only modest differences in the probability of reaching or remaining in the top category.

Figure 2: Predicted probabilities of research rank.

4. Discussion

This study contributes to the growing body of research on academic mobility by shifting attention from international moves, dominant in the literature, to the within-country mobility of researchers in a middle-income setting, using open administrative data from MinCiencias. By modelling rank outcomes in the Colombian evaluation system (Junior > Associate > Senior) as a function of mobility and a set of lagged individual, institutional, and contextual covariates, the analysis provides evidence on how geographic relocation across Colombian cities is associated with subsequent career performance in a policy-relevant classification framework.

A first descriptive finding is the limited prevalence of inter-city mobility: only 2.7% of researcher–call observations involve a city change between consecutive assessment calls. This low rate is consistent with the idea that national academic labor markets can exhibit substantial “spatial inertia,” especially when research capacity and employment opportunities are concentrated in a few large hubs. Mobility is strongly age- and career-stage graded: Junior researchers are overrepresented among movers (67.3% of movers vs 48.6% overall), while Seniors are underrepresented (10.5% of movers vs 19.8% overall). This pattern aligns with theories of cumulative advantage and the “settling” of scientists as they accumulate location-specific capital (networks, supervisory roles, labs, and reputational assets), which increases the opportunity cost of relocation later in the career.

The core substantive result concerns the association between geographic mobility and subsequent rank. The proportional odds assumption does not hold, motivating the use of an unrestricted ordinal specification that allows heterogeneous effects across thresholds. The unrestricted model provides a better fit than the restricted proportional odds model.

While coefficient patterns for *moved* differ across thresholds in the unrestricted model, the marginal probability analysis clarifies the substantive direction: mobility is not associated with sped up promotion, and instead correlates with *rank instability*, particularly at the bottom and middle of the distribution. Among researchers previously classified as Junior, movers display an even higher probability of remaining Junior; among those previously classified as Associate, mobility is associated with a higher likelihood of being reclassified as Junior rather than promoted to Senior.

This finding contrasts with evidence from some high-income settings where movers (especially those moving to more research-intensive environments) often experience citation or productivity gains. It is, however, consistent with the idea that mobility can be disruptive when moves are driven by precarious employment, short-term contracts, or necessity rather than strategic career investment. In the Colombian case, geographic relocation may reflect constrained local opportunities, institutional turnover, or mismatches between researcher specialization and the local research ecosystem, mechanisms that can reduce short-run output and weaken the continuity needed to satisfy evaluation criteria. The fact that MinCiencias rank progression does not directly translate into salary or institutional career advancement may further reduce incentives for institutions to protect research time and resources during a relocation, potentially amplifying short-term performance costs.

A second plausible mechanism is *timing*: MinCiencias assessments occur in discrete calls (2013, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2019, 2021). If relocation imposes a temporary productivity dip or delays in documenting outputs within CvLAC, the next assessment may capture disruption more readily than longer-term gains, especially if the benefits of a new environment (new collaborations, lab access, funding) accrue with a lag. The observed association may reflect the short-to-medium-term consequences of moving rather than the longer-run returns.

Institutional context emerges as one of the strongest correlations of rank outcomes. The concentration of academic capital (rank concentration within the prior institution) shows large and statistically significant effects in the unrestricted model. This pattern is consistent with cumulative advantage at the organizational level: researchers embedded in environments with a higher density of senior peers may gain access to mentoring, co-authorship opportunities, infrastructure, and reputational spillovers that facilitate success under national evaluation criteria.

At the same time, this finding raises a policy-relevant interpretation: evaluation systems may inadvertently reinforce institutional hierarchies if recognized researchers and recognized institutions mutually amplify each other's status. The descriptive evidence of strong attraction toward major hubs (e.g., Bogotá and Antioquia (i.e., Medellín) further suggest the potential for a self-reinforcing geography of scientific capital, where mobility primarily reallocates talent toward already dominant centers rather than diffusing capacity across the territory.

The contextual unemployment rate is included as a proxy for city-level labor market pressure. Results indicate that unemployment is associated with rank transitions in a career-stage-dependent manner: for Juniors, higher unemployment appears to be linked to upward movement, plausibly reflecting intensified efforts to secure academic standing when outside options are scarce. For higher ranks, associations are weaker and less systematic. These patterns underscore that “mobility

and performance” are embedded in broader local opportunity structures, and that early-career researchers may be particularly sensitive to non-academic labor market conditions.

Taken together, the findings suggest that simply encouraging geographic mobility is unlikely to be sufficient, and may even be counterproductive for some groups, unless moves are accompanied by institutional supports that prevent short-run disruption from translating into evaluation penalties.

Policy implications that follow directly from the evidence include: (i) Targeted support during transitions, since if mobility is associated with retention in Junior ranks and downgrading for Associates, then relocation packages, bridge funding, and protected research time could be prioritized for movers to reduce transition costs; (ii) Attention to mid-career vulnerability, since the instability among Associate movers suggests a “risk zone” in which relocation may not be rewarded and may even be penalized; (iii) Monitoring institutional concentration dynamics, since strong institutional effects and hub concentration call for policy instruments that build research capacity outside dominant cities; otherwise, mobility may deepen regional inequalities in scientific production and recognition; (iv) Evaluation timing and lag structures, because mobility-related benefits may take time to materialize, evaluation frameworks could consider mechanisms to avoid penalizing short-term output disruption following a move (e.g., allowing a transition window or emphasizing multi-year output trajectories).

5. Conclusions

This paper examined how within-country geographic mobility between Colombian cities is associated with subsequent research performance, measured through MinCiencias researcher ranks, using a large administrative dataset covering multiple national assessment calls. Mobility events are uncommon (2.7% of observations), and movers are disproportionately early-career researchers. The main conclusion is that mobility is not linked to a general promotion premium in the MinCiencias ranking system. Instead, predicted probability patterns indicate that Junior movers are more likely to remain Junior, and Associate movers face an elevated risk of being reclassified as Junior rather than advancing to Senior, suggesting that mobility is associated with instability rather than rapid upward progression.

Beyond mobility, institutional context plays a central role: greater concentration of senior researchers in the prior institution is strongly associated with higher rank outcomes, consistent with cumulative advantage at the organizational level. Local labor market conditions also matter, but primarily for early-career researchers, for whom higher unemployment appears to be associated with upward rank movement, plausibly reflecting heightened effort to secure academic standing under constrained opportunities.

These findings should be interpreted within the study’s constraints. First, mobility is measured as a change of city between assessment calls, which cannot capture interim moves, commuting, temporary placements, or the exact timing of relocation within the interval. Second, the analysis is explicitly associative: mobility decisions are likely endogenous, and available data do not support causal identification via instruments or exogenous shocks. Third, the outcome is a national administrative ranking that may reflect reporting practices and system-specific incentives, and it is not designed to map one-to-one onto conventional bibliometric measures of impact.

Future research could: (i) incorporate distance and destination characteristics (including institutional change vs within-institution relocation); (ii) model longer-run trajectories to test whether mobility’s potential benefits emerge with delay; (iii) integrate publication/citation data to compare “rank effects” with bibliometric effects; and (iv) explore quasi-experimental designs

where feasible to address selection into mobility. Finally, Colombia's distinctive history of internal displacement raises a broader agenda: distinguishing voluntary academic mobility from relocation driven by insecurity or institutional instability could further clarify when mobility functions as an opportunity versus a constraint.

Overall, the evidence suggests that in Colombia's research evaluation context, geographic mobility is best understood not as an automatic accelerator of career performance, but as an event that interacts with career stage, institutional stratification, and local opportunity structures, implying that policy efforts to promote mobility should be paired with safeguards and supports that prevent relocation costs from translating into rank penalties.¹

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